

**EXPLAINABLE MACHINE LEARNING
FRAMEWORK FOR CNT-PCM THERMAL
CONDUCTIVITY PREDICTION**

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2. Materials and Methods

Mathematical Formulation

Eq. (1) represents the effective thermal conductivity of the nano-enhanced PCM was calculated using Fourier's law of heat conduction [6]

$$k_{eff} = \frac{qL}{A\Delta T} \quad (1)$$

While Eq. (2) demonstrates the enhancement ratio evaluation method [7]

$$\text{Enhancement ratio} = \frac{k_{eff}}{k_m} \quad (2)$$

2.2 Data Pre-processing

The dataset was refined through noise removal, handling missing values, feature engineering and selection, normalization, standardization, correlation analysis, and variance inflation assessment to ensure data quality and stability.

The box plots shows the statistical distribution of all input parameters (PCM thermal conductivity, CNT thermal conductivity, CNT length, diameter, and volume fraction) along with the output variable (thermal conductivity enhancement ratio) for both the actual and modified datasets. In the actual dataset, the variables show broader range, reflecting natural experimental variations and differences in material properties and operating conditions. Whereas, the modified dataset shows a finer distribution, with reduced variation in some parameters due to preprocessing steps such as normalization, scaling, and outlier removal. The median values remains nearly unchanged in both datasets, shows that the overall trend is preserved after modification. Slight changes in the interquartile range (IQR) suggest better data balance and consistency. Furthermore, no extreme outliers are observed in the modified dataset, illustrating better statistical stability.

In general, the comparative box plot analysis ensures that preprocessing improves data stability while retaining the physical significance of both input variables and the enhancement ratio, thereby supporting robust model development.

Fig. 1 Comparative box plot illustration of (a) Actual length collected from literatures (b) Modified length after removal of outliers

Fig. 2 Comparative box plot illustration of (a) Actual diameter collected from literatures (b) Modified diameter after removal of outliers

Fig. 3 Comparative box plot demonstrates (a) Actual volume fraction collected from literatures (b) Modified volume fraction after pre-processing

Fig. 4 Comparative box plot demonstrates (a) Actual PCM thermal conductivity obtained from literatures (b) Modified PCM thermal conductivity after removal of outlier

Fig. 5 Comparative box plot demonstrates (a) Actual CNT (Nanoparticle) thermal conductivity obtained from literatures (b) Modified CNT thermal conductivity after outlier removal

OUTPUT FEATURES

Fig. 6 Comparative box plot demonstrates (a) Actual Thermal conductivity Enhancement ratio (k_{eff}/k_m) (b) Modified Thermal conductivity Enhancement ratio (k_{eff}/k_m) after outlier removal

2.4.1 Evaluation Metrics

Whereas, the statistical definition of R^2 and MSE are implemented in this research follows the formulation stated in [8].

Eq. (3) represents the mathematical equation to calculate R^2 ,

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N [(y)_{Lit. inf.} - (y)_{BBEMT pred.}]^2}{\sum_{i=1}^N [(y)_{Lit. inf.} - (y)_{avg.}]^2} \quad (3)$$

Eq. (4) represents the mathematical equation to calculate MSE,

$$MSE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N [(y)_{Lit. inf.} - (y)_{BBEMT}]^2 \quad (4)$$

3. Results and Discussion

3.3 Evaluation of the proposed framework

(a) Bayesian Regularization

Fig 1- Regression plot of Bayesian Regularization (BR) model shows the correlation between experimental and predicted values.

The figure illustrates the Regression plot of Bayesian Regularization model which demonstrates strong predictive capability, with correlation of R=0.988 for training, R=0.94 for testing and R=0.97 for overall dataset. The relationship between the training and testing R values shows good generalization with minimal overfitting.

Fig 2- Error Histogram of BR

Fig 3- Performance plot of BR

Fig 4- Training state of BR

Model Summary

Train a neural network to map predictors to continuous responses.

Data
 Predictors: inputs - [5x502 double]
 Responses: output - [1x502 double]
 Inputs: double array of 502 observations with 5 features.
 Output: double array of 502 observations with 1 features.

Algorithm
 Data division: Random
 Training algorithm: Bayesian regularization
 Performance: Mean squared error

Training Results
 Training start time: 18-Feb-2026 23:02:03
 Layer size: 15

	Observations	MSE	R
Training	427	0.0054	0.9881
Validation	0	NaN	NaN
Test	75	0.0354	0.9412

Training data: 75 %
 Validation data: 10
 Test data: 15

SPLIT BUILD

Fig 5- Summary of BR model

(b) Levenberg- Marquardt

Fig 6- Regression plot of Levenberg- Marquardt (LM) model shows the correlation between experimental and predicted values

The figure illustrates the Regression plot of Levenberg-Marquardt model which demonstrates strong predictive capability, with correlation of $R=0.92$ for training, $R=0.88$ for validation, $R=0.87$ for testing and $R=0.918$ as overall regression for the datasets. The relationship between the training and testing R values shows good generalization with minimal overfitting.

Fig 7- Error Histogram of LM

Fig 8- Performance plot of LM

Fig 9- Training state of LM

Model Summary ⋮

Train a neural network to map predictors to continuous responses.

Data
 Predictors: inputs - [5x502 double]
 Responses: output - [1x502 double]
 inputs: double array of 502 observations with 5 features.
 output: double array of 502 observations with 1 features.

Algorithm
 Data division: Random
 Training algorithm: Levenberg-Marquardt
 Performance: Mean squared error

Training Results
 Training start time: 18-Feb-2026 23:20:32
 Layer size: 15

	Observations	MSE	R
Training	377	0.0356	0.9279
Validation	50	0.0339	0.8883
Test	75	0.0425	0.8753

Training data: 75 %

Validation data: ⬆️ ⬇️ ⬆️ Layer size: ⬆️ ⬇️ ⬆️

Test data: ⬆️ ⬇️ ⬆️

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Fig 10- Summary of LM model

(c) Scaled Conjugate gradient

Fig 11- Regression plot of Scaled Conjugate Gradient (SCG) model shows the correlation between experimental and predicted values

The figure illustrates the Regression plot of Scaled Conjugate Gradient model which demonstrates strong predictive capability, with correlation of $R=0.792$ for training, $R=0.71$ $R=0.792$ for testing and $R= 0.783$ as overall regression for the datasets. The relationship between the training and testing R values shows good generalization with minimal overfitting.

Fig 12- Error Histogram of SCG

Fig 13- Performance plot of SCG

Fig 14- Training state of SCG

Fig 15- Summary of SCG model

5. Future Work

Future research will focus on increasing the experimental datasets to include a wide range of nanoparticle morphologies, dispersion conditions, and temperature-dependent thermophysical properties to improve model generalization. The development of physics-informed and uncertainty-aware learning frameworks will be explored to enhance extrapolation capability beyond the trained parameter space. Using statistical approaches and uncertainty analysis will enhance the accuracy of predictions under various experimental conditions. Further, advanced ensemble and hybrid models will be perused to ensure better stability and dependable performance. In conclusion, integration of the predictive framework with optimization

algorithms for material design and thermal system performance enhancement will be pursued to facilitate practical engineering implementation.